

Content Based Product Recommendation in E-commerce

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Abstract—The recommendation system is a significant technique used in different E-commerce systems. As E-commerce continues to flourish, more and more people are choosing to shop online, which has led to a vast selection of products available for purchase. To help consumers traverse through this immense array of products, the recommendation system is utilized to suggest items based on the user's preferences and past behavior. This technology assists users in finding fitting products that they may not have discovered on their own, making their shopping experience more efficient and enjoyable. This paper covers the topic of content-based recommendation systems, which are outlined to recommend items to users based on the elucidation of the item and the user's interests. In order to implement content-based product recommendation, this method relies on techniques such as TF-IDF (Term Frequency Inverse Document Frequency) and Cosine Similarity, to dictate the importance of a product to a user's interests. By using these methods content-based recommendation systems can provide customized recommendations that agree with the user's distinctive bias and interests.

Keywords— Recommendation systems, Content based filtering, TF-IDF, Cosine similarity

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommendation systems are methods or techniques that suggest personalized items to users based on their previous interactions and preferences. These systems make use of machine learning and data mining algorithms which examine user data such as search history, purchase records, and ratings to detect patterns and trends that can be used to provide suggestions. They are frequently used in various industries, including E-commerce, social media, online entertainment services etc. to escalate user satisfaction and engagement. Here, in this paper the system analyzes the characteristics of items the user has shown interest in and suggests similar items based on these characteristics. For example, if a user has previously shown interest in a certain type of product, the system would recommend products with similar attributes or from the same category. Machine learning algorithms are used to identify patterns and relationships between item attributes. The aim is to provide personalized recommendations to users based on their preferences and past behavior, and to help them discover new items they may like.

The paper proposes the utilization of recommendation systems for suggesting E-commerce products to users based on their preferences, search and browsing history, product descriptions, categories, subcategories, as well as each product's keywords and unique characteristics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sunkuru Gopal Krishna Patro et al. [1] introduces a novel recommendation system named HAR-KNN, which aims to overcome challenges in existing approaches by integrating the K-NN algorithm with a user behavior matrix. The K-NN algorithm generates a feature vector for each user's behavior records and samples similar purchase intentions to analyze the attributes of many users. This allows for accurate prediction of recommendations and categorization of user goals to recommend accurate predictions. The paper explores different combinations of this approach to improve recommendation accuracy, and its effectiveness is demonstrated using multi-attribute behavior data from a real E-commerce site.

Umair Javed et al. [2] the survey paper is about content based filtering on recommendation systems. The authors present a context-aware recommender system that filters items associated with the user's interests and recommends those items. They use different techniques, including content-based and collaborative filtering, to filter e-learning content and deliver convenient news to users. The authors also use various technologies such as natural ontology languages then semantic mapping rules, java and machine learning. On applying semantic approach, it was found that it works like content-based recommender system and recommends items considering users interests.

Bandyopadhyay et al. [3] discusses an approach that uses Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) to recommend similar products to student groups based on their buying patterns. The goal of the approach is to satisfy the needs of every customer. Time-series data is used to predict the appropriate data using ANN, and the prediction error can be estimated. Historical data is used to generate product predictions, which

can be refined using online reviews. The collected data is pre-processed to remove unwanted information.

Ji et al. [4] proposed a Hybrid Recommendation model that incorporates customer ratings, reviews, and social data. The model consists of several stages, including feature generation, review transformation, model training, community detection, feature blending, and prediction and evaluation. Through examination, the model is used to pinpoint and inspect review content to determine social networks using convolutional recommendation models, such as network-based models. The outcome indicate that recommendation accuracy can be notably improved by exploiting review texts and social networks.

Debashis Das et al. [5] paper explains about recommendation systems which help customers make knowledgeable decisions by recommending items based on their likes, even if they don't have complete understanding about a particular item. These systems can be used in a variety of ways to help users' sort through large amounts of information and find what they need. They are software tools that filter personalized information based on the user's preferences, in order to suggest new items that may be of interest. It is important to accurately understand the user's preferences to provide the most relevant suggestions. This survey paper discusses and compares various types of recommender systems, as well as popular recommendation algorithms and their applications.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The RS i.e. the Recommendation Systems can be of three types. It can be Content-based Filtering, Collaborative Filtering or Hybrid Recommendation Systems. Here, in this paper we are going to concentrate on Content-based Recommendation Systems.

Fig 1: Content-Based Recommendation

The system looks into the characteristics or specific features of items the user has shown interest before and suggests similar items based on these characteristics. For example, in the website I have created, which is for selling handcrafted items, suppose a customer have previously viewed the details of certain products say, Fine Glass Curio-Owl, the most then the products category, subcategory, keywords of that particular item and it's features are compared against all other products in the dataset to search for similarity.

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Then the similarity scores are sorted such that first ten products with more similarity score is recommended to the user as they are sharing similar characteristics. Machine learning algorithms are used to identify patterns and relationships between item attributes. The ultimate aim is to provide a personalized recommendation to users based on their preferences and past behavior, and to help them explore new items which they may like most probably.

	c_id	p_id	req_id
1	15	19	
2	15	19	
4	28	19	
8	15	19	
9	28	19	
10	28	19	
11	15	19	
16	28	19	
17	28	19	

Fig 2: User browsing history, tbl_click

The techniques used are TF-IDF and Cosine Similarity. Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a specialized area within the field of artificial intelligence that focuses on comprehending and handling human language. With the emergence of recent advancements in machine learning, numerous companies have started implementing the principles of natural language processing to their operations. Term frequency refers to the frequency of a word in a document, expressed as the ratio of the number of times the word appears to the total number of words in the document. It is a measure used in natural language processing and information retrieval to quantify the occurrence of a specific word within a given document. Each document has its own distinct term frequency, representing the relative importance or prevalence of a word within that particular document.

$$tf_{i,j} = \frac{n_{i,j}}{\sum_k n_{i,j}}$$

Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) is a logarithmic measure used in natural language processing and information retrieval to evaluate the significance of a word in a collection of documents. It is calculated by taking the logarithm of the ratio between the total number of documents in the corpus and the number of documents that contain a specific word. The IDF value provides a measure of how rare or common a word is across the entire corpus. It is used to give weights to words, giving higher importance to infrequent words that appear in fewer documents and lower significance to common words that appear frequently in many documents.

$$idf(w) = \log\left(\frac{N}{df_t}\right)$$

The TF-IDF is the product of TF and TDF i.e. TF*IDF, to calculate the TF-IDF scores of every word in the corpus.

$$w_{i,j} = tf_{i,j} \times \log\left(\frac{N}{df_i}\right)$$

The cosine similarity is calculated by taking the dot product of the two vectors and dividing them by the product of their magnitudes. This gives the cosine of the angle between the vectors, where the angle (represented by θ) ranges from 0 to 90 degrees. Since tf-idf vectors are non-negative, the angle between them can only range from 0 to 90 degrees, and the cosine of the angle ranges from 1 to 0. This range shows how close two products are. If q and $d2$ are tf-idf vectors, then

$$\cos \theta = \frac{d_2 \cdot q}{\|d_2\| \|q\|}$$

The paper is proposed keeping in mind that the utilization of recommendation systems for suggesting E-commerce products to users based on their preferences such that they could know more products according their taste in shopping.

IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTAION

The goal of this work is to develop a Recommendation System which primarily focuses on users interests and taste in product selection by making using of Content-based approach in Recommendation Systems. In order to do so the following steps are followed.

A. Data Collection

We have a dataset containing details of the product. The columns are index, id, pdt_name, category, subcategory, no_of_sales, keywords, dealer, color, and description. For building the system we need attributes category, subcategory, keywords, description and color as feature set.

Fig 3: Dataset

B. Data Preparation

This is an important stage in machine learning. This step comprises cleaning of data, data transformation, data reduction and so on to make our recommendations more precise. Here elimination of unwanted entries i.e. removal noisy data is done. Stop words are also removed from the dataset to tidy it up. All of these steps are done to improve the data's effectiveness.

```

4 4 121 Wooden Miniature Musical Instrument Curio-Star wooden miniature 14 Wooden Miniature Musical Instrument Star Deco Thomas T Brown Wooden Miniature Musical Instrument Curio-Star

product_data.shape
(74, 10)

vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer(stop_words='english')

selected_features = ['category', 'subcategory', 'keywords', 'dealer', 'color', 'description']
print(selected_features)

['category', 'subcategory', 'keywords', 'dealer', 'color', 'description']

for feature in selected_features:
    product_data[feature] = product_data[feature].fillna("")

combined_features = product_data['category'] + "-" + product_data['subcategory'] + "-" + product_data['keywords'] + "-" + product_data['dealer'] + "-" + product_data['color'] + "-" + product_data['description']
    
```

Fig 4: Preparing data

C. Model Building

The model building is the very important step for the recommendation.

1. Firstly, we will open a flask project and import all the necessary packages. In order to implement into the PHP project, the model building is done in flask project and connected to the project using curl where the result is returned back i.e. the recommended products to the PHP project in JSON format.
2. The dataset is read and the machine learning codes to perform the content-based suggestions are written using TF-IDF and Cosine similarity inside a function which is invoked when a user clicks 'My Recommendation' link in the project.

```

feature_vectors = vectorizer.fit_transform(Combined_features)
similarity = cosine_similarity(feature_vectors)

similarity.shape
product_name = "Fine Glass Curio-Owl"
list_of_all_titles = product_data['pdt_name'].tolist()
find_close_match = difflib.get_close_matches(product_name, list_of_all_titles)
close_match = find_close_match[0]
index_of_the_product = product_data[product_data.pdt_name == close_match][['index']].values[0]
similarity_score = list(enumerate(similarity[index_of_the_product]))
len(similarity_score)
sorted_similar_products = sorted(similarity_score, key=lambda x: x[1], reverse=True)
    
```

Fig 5: Building model

D. Training and Analysing

The model's performance is analyzed and trained using a sample product and checked whether the recommended items are similar to that product or not.

```

i = 1
for movie in sorted_similar_products:
    index = movie[0]
    title_from_index = product_data[product_data.index==index][['pdt_name']].values[0]
    if (i<11):
        print(i, '.', title_from_index)
        i+=1
    
```

Products suggested for you :

1. Fine Glass Curio-Owl
2. Fine Glass Curio-Elephant
3. Fine Glass Curio-Peacock
4. Fine Glass Curio-Tortoise
5. Fine Glass Curio-Deer
6. Fine Glass Curio Musical Instrument-Tanpura
7. Fine Glass Musical Instruments-Shehnai
8. coconut Craft Curio-Teapot
9. Handcrafted Wooden Solitaire Game
10. Handcrafted Wooden Box

Fig 6: Training

E. Evaluation

Finally, the testing is done inside the project, to check whether a product is suggested according to a customer's likes. The most browsed product from the user's history is

used to recommend other products which he/she may like as well.

V. RESULT

In this paper, we develop a recommendation system that uses Cosine Similarity and content-based filtering to recommend products to users based on their interests. The code is executed in Python Flask and connected to the php project using curl. The users browsing history is stored in MySQL database associated with the project. The most searched product is then selected using query and passed to Flask function to recommend related products. The dataset contains different products in different varieties and it is classified and correctly recommended to users based on their interests.

Products suggested for you:
Coconut Craft Table Lamp
Coconut Craft Hanging Tier Lamp
Coconut Craft Curio-Teapot
Coconut Craft Tea Light Holder-Dots and Dashes
Coconut Craft Tea Light Holder-Slits
Coconut Craft Soap Dishes
Coconut Craft Dessert Serving Bowls & Spoons
Coconut Shell Wooden Tea Cups
Bamboo Pen Stand
Wooden Elephant Pen Stand

Fig 7: Recommendation of product similar to his interests with reference to his browsing history.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the internet era, recommendation systems have emerged as the single most important component of an accurate and trustworthy information source.

Most recommendation systems try to anticipate the buyer's interests and then suggest products in that manner. To give recommendations to the intended consumers, this

paper used a content-based filtering technique. The availability of the contents characterizing the objects and users' interest profiles resulted to a solution to this issue. Although they rely on these contents, content-based approaches are not influenced by user ratings. In addition, an algorithm for offering or suggesting recommendations based on user queries is presented in this work. The approach uses the cosine similarity metric in addition to TF-IDF weighing.

The outcomes of the research demonstrate that the suggested strategy offers relevant suggestions. The presented work can be used to suggest other domains like movies, music, and other media in various sectors.

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